

RESEARCH WORK OF THE ALL-COMPOSITE FUSELAGE STRUCTURE

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1. ABSTRACT

Honda R&D is developing a proof-of-concept business jet that utilizes an all-composite fuselage. The main feature of this fuselage structure is that the stiffened panel and the sandwich panel are co-cured integrally in an autoclave to reduce both weight and cost. Another key feature is that a buckling tolerance design is adopted for the skin. This means that shear buckling is allowed beyond 50% limit load. The material and structural tests of the composite fuselage were conducted applying the concept of “Building Block Approach”. The purposes of these tests were to prove safety of flight for the composite fuselage and to verify the accuracy of the finite element analysis and other analyses. First the design allowables of the materials were decided by coupon tests. Environmental, damage tolerance, and fatigue conditions were considered. Three major component tests were conducted. The fuselage was divided into the nose, cabin, and tail components and each component was tested separately. Structurally critical elements and sub-components were selected and tested prior to the component tests. The new curing system for the sandwich panel under high pressure was developed to make the large integrally co-cured sandwich and stiffened skin panel. Several patent pending affordable process technologies were also developed in the field of lay up and structural bonding.

KEYWORDS: fuselage, sandwich panel, stiffened panel, buckling, processing, structural test, building block approach

2. INTRODUCTION

Currently composite structures for general aviation utilize an all-sandwich panel structure. This structure is effective in reducing the cost and development time due to a simple manufacturing process and a reduction in the number of molds and other manufacturing tools. However, the weight savings compared with conventional aluminum construction are not enough. In addition, there are difficulties with quality control and installation of some equipment.

In 1993, the first flight of an all-composite research jet MH-02 [1] was performed successfully. The MH-02 was designed and fabricated as an all-sandwich panel structure. Structural weight did not meet program goals. Hence the barrel components with co-cured stiffened panel structure (so called black aluminum) were designed, analyzed, fabricated, and tested to evaluate the weight reduction and manufacturing process. It was proven that this structure is more effective for weight reduction but it leads to high manufacturing cost if it is applied to a three-dimensional contour.

We, therefore, selected a new concept of the all-composite fuselage structure for a new proof-of-concept business jet which is currently in development. This paper describes the design of the composite fuselage structure, affordable process technologies, and the procedure of assuring safety of flight.

3. FUSELAGE STRUCTURE

The entire fuselage structure is fabricated of carbon/epoxy composite except for windows, windshields, and some fittings that carry concentrated heavy loads. The cabin section is pressurized, and utilizes a clamshell type passenger door and plug type emergency exit. Design requirements are

based upon FAR Part 23.

The feature of this fuselage structure (Fig.1) is that the stiffened panel and sandwich panel are co-cured integrally in an autoclave to reduce both weight and manufacturing cost. The stiffened panel structure reduces weight because of its high efficiency in the simple cylindrical cabin portion. The sandwich panel structure reduces cost because it is easy to fabricate the three-dimensional contour of the nose, cockpit, and tail portion. To realize this new concept structure, a high pressure curing system was necessary for the sandwich panel. Because the curing pressure for a sandwich panel is generally less than half of that for a solid laminate to prevent from core crush.

Another feature is that the buckling tolerance design was adopted for the skin of the stiffened panel. Shear buckling was allowed beyond 50% limit load and compression buckling was allowed beyond 100% limit load. The skin thickness and the ply orientation of each bay were decided optimally by considering the stress level and the load direction to meet the design criteria as close as possible. Several full scale curved stiffened panels were also fabricated, and sub-component shear buckling tests were conducted [2] to verify the post buckling behavior and the final strength.

The skin panel consists of only two pieces, left hand side and right hand side, and they were bonded at the top and bottom single lap splices. Hence there is no longitudinal joint except for the radome and the tailcone.

Both structural efficiency and manufacturing process were considered to select the stringer and frame section profile. Fig.2 shows the stringer and frame cross-sections and the general configuration of inter sections of them. A skin, stringers, and frame T-members were integrally co-cured with the sandwich panel portion in one shot as an entire skin panel. Frame L-members were bonded when entire left and right hand side skin panels were assembled to simplify co-curing process. Heavily loaded interface frames (C-section) were also bonded to the skin panels at the same time. The height of the frame was limited up to 45mm for the cabin space. Therefore, the high modulus laminate (more than 80000 MPa) was selected for the frame flange. The honeycomb thickness of 20 mm was selected due to the bending stress from the pressurized load.

A trade study was conducted to compare the weight of three fuselages for the reference model of a small business jet:

- 1) A conventional aluminum structure
- 2) A composite sandwich panel structure
- 3) The new concept sandwich and stiffened panel structure

Results of this study are shown in Fig.3. The weight reduction of the new concept structure was about 20% compared with a conventional aluminum structure, however that of a composite sandwich panel structure was about 15%. We, furthermore, achieved to keep the weight of the fuselage within a design target successfully.

Fig.1 Structural Concept of All-Composite Fuselage

Fig.2

Fig.3 Weight Comparison of the Fuselages

4. MATERIAL AND PROCESSING

4.1 Materials

The material used for the fuselage structure was 180°C curing epoxy prepreg reinforced by unidirectional and woven carbon fibers. The fibers were TOHO G30-500 (high strength and intermediate modulus), and the epoxy system was CYTEC 5276-1 (high damage tolerance and good durability under hot/wet environment). For sandwich panel fabrication, Nomex honeycombs and FM300 (180°C curing epoxy film adhesives) were used. On the outer surface, expanded copper foil with resin film was laid up to protect the fuselage from lightning strikes.

4.2 Fabrication

To reduce labor-intensive operations from all phases of composite fabrication for the new concept structure, several new manufacturing processes were developed as follows:

- A) Press forming technique for pre-compaction parts with pre-laminate
- B) Step forming technique for joggle of pre-compaction parts
- C) Edge trimming technique for honeycomb with plugged freeze gel
- D) Fabrication technique for glass prepreg tool which considered thermal expansion
- E) Co-curing technique of stiffened panel and sandwich panel: The new curing system for the sandwich panel under high pressure

The following are detail explanation of A) and E).

A) Press forming technique for pre-compaction parts with pre-laminates

The stiffened panel was co-cured in this fuselage. The stringers of the stiffened panel were prepared by pre-compaction before co-curing. Generally composite parts are laminated layer by layer by hand lay-up, then vacuum bagged and heated. Labor costs of these processes are high. Instead of hand lay-up, press forming by using pre-laminates was developed as shown in Fig.4. In advance, large sheets of pre-laminates were prepared. Next the pre-laminates were cut all together with an automated cutting machine, then the pieces were heated up to 90°C. Finally, the pieces were pressed and formed in the mold at 40°C. The labor hours were reduced to 1/5 compared to ordinary processes.

Fig.4 Pre-laminate and Press Forming Technique

E) Co-curing technique of stiffened panel and sandwich panel

Integrally co-cured composite structures are effective to reduce the number of parts and work load. The skin panels (Fig.5) which had both stiffened panel areas and sandwich panel areas were produced by a co-curing process. In this process, both the sandwich panel and the stiffened panel were co-cured at the same pressure, 0.6 MPa. To prevent core crush of the sandwich panel under high pressure without weight penalty such as potting compound filled in honeycomb-edge, a new method of edge stabilization was developed. This new process consists of overlaying a picture frame on the edges of the sandwich panel as shown in Fig.6. By locating a picture frame around the honeycomb core to stop the slippage of prepreg, core crush could be prevented. This technique made it possible to cure the stiffened panel and sandwich panel simultaneously.

Fig.5 Skin Panel

4.3 Airframe Assembly

The primary structure of the fuselage was bonded with 120°C curing epoxy film adhesive. The assembly methods/jigs to keep the dimensional accuracy and contact pressure during bonding processes were developed. Fig.7 shows the fuselage assembly jig which was designed to keep accurate geometry of the fuselage at 120°C. The assembly jig consisted of CFRP parts and steel parts with slide mechanism. By the slide mechanism, the jig prevented slippage due to the difference of thermal expansion between CFRP and steel. Fig.8 and Fig.9 show methods of applying contact pressure for a bonded assembly. The magnetic force of neodymium magnets were used at right and left skin bonded joint, and the hoop tension of CFRP bands were used at bonded ring frames assembly. These techniques were used to reduce assembly labor hours by one-third of the traditional way. Also the dimensional accuracy of critical points such as wing and empennage interfaces were within ±0.5 mm (Fig.10).

Fig.7 CFRP/Steel Assembly Jig

HT SAFETY ASSURANCE

5.1 Procedure

The material and structural tests of the composite fuselage were conducted applying the concept of “Building Block Approach” based on AC20-107 [3]. They comprised coupon, element, sub-component, and component tests. The purposes of these material and structural tests were to determine design allowables, to verify the accuracy of the FE analyses, to prove safety of flight for the composite fuselage. Furthermore, the proof test for flight was conducted to confirm the reparability of the strain results.

5.2 Design Allowables and Coupon Tests

Material design allowables were considered “Damage to environment condition (temperature and humidity)”, and “No-growth damage under the test”. A lot of data from coupon tests were obtained for these purposes. Fig.11 shows the relations between compressive failure strain and compressive failure strain.

and impact damage under hot-wet conditions. We determined the compressive allowable strain with this test data by considering barely visible impact damage.

5.2 Element Tests

Seventeen structural elements were selected and tested. The most important purpose of the element tests was to prove the strength of several specific and critical bonded joints under the hot-wet condition with an artificial damage, because accurate analysis of a bonded joint strength is difficult. Other specific elements were tested such as the cut-out in the heavily loaded frame web, the skin joggle around the windshields, the transition area between sandwich and stiffened panel, the mechanical single shear joint in the anisotropic laminates, and so forth. In addition, a lightning strike test was conducted to determine the protection system. Expanded copper foil with film resin showed good protection capability with minimum weight penalty.

5.3 Sub-Component Tests

Structurally critical sub-components were selected and tested prior to the component tests. Five sub-components and test subjects were as follows:

- 1) Stiffened panel (shear buckling, compression buckling, and static test)
- 2) Stiffened panel with a window (shear buckling and static test)
- 3) Passenger door (static, fail-safe, and fatigue/damage tolerance test)
- 4) Wing-fuselage fitting (static and fatigue/damage tolerance test)
- 5) Windshield (static and fail-safe test)

The shear buckling test of the stiffened panel was conducted to verify the post-buckling design and load carrying capability after buckling (Fig.12). The sub-components were 0.8 m squared curved panels with the same structural detail and manufacturing process as the actual structure. The loading picture frame was modified to prevent it from warping due to curvature of the panel. Buckling load of FEA showed good agreement with the test result. Final strength of the panel with a barely visible damage was at least 4.5 times higher than the buckling load. The failure mode was the compressive failure of the skin. Until the collapse, the obvious delamination between the skin and stiffener was not observed.

Fig.12 Shear Buckling Test of Stiffened Panel

The passenger door was fabricated and tested (Fig.13) to prove the durability for three lives, integrity of door support structure, and airtightness for pressurization. The door was installed in the steel pressure vessel and applied cyclic pressurized load from a blower. These test results showed the door structure had the fatigue strength, fail safe strength, and good damage tolerance capability except for the metal lugs. These parts were modified prior to the component test.

Fig.13 Passenger Door Sub-component Test

5.4 Component Tests

Considering the manufacturing facilities, functions of the fuselage, and project time frame, the fuselage was divided into three major components and tested as follows:

- 1) Nose component (nose landing gear load static test)
- 2) Cabin component (flight load static test, pressurized load static test, and pressurized load fatigue

/damage tolerance test)

3) Tail component (flight load static test)

Due to the limited test facilities, component tests were conducted at room temperature and humidity. A knock down factor was considered to the applied loads to cover environmental effects.

The cabin component is the pressurized section between front and rear bulkheads of 5.8 m length with the passenger door, emergency exit, windshields, and windows. The major objectives of the cabin component test were to measure skin buckling load and verify the accuracy of the post buckling design, to verify the accuracy of FEA by measuring the strain, displacement, and reaction force, and to prove static and three lives pressurized fatigue strength. The test procedure was as follows:

- 1) Limit load test with four flight load cases and pressurization
- 2) Three lives pressurized load fatigue test with barely visible impact damages at critical points
- 3) Residual strength test

Five servo-controlled hydraulic actuators simulated the flight loads and a blower applied the pressurized load (Fig.14). Fig.17 shows the buckling behavior at the limit load. The shear buckling occurred at the design target as shown in Fig.16. Strain gage data showed the error of FEA was less than ten percent at typical locations. It was proven that the impact damages did not grow under the cyclic pressurized load. By the way, cracks were found in metal door parts, acrylic windshield, and a few fasteners. Some of them were modified during the tests. After the fatigue test, the residual strength test was completed successfully.

The tail component was 2.6 m long and included the installation of a dummy aluminum empennage. The primary objective of the tail component test was to prove the strength of the fuselage-empennage connection. Front end of the component was clamped to the test frame and loads were applied through the dummy empennage by six hydraulic actuators (Fig.15). Three critical load cases were selected and limit load test was conducted. Buckling occurred around inside connection structure. After laminate plates were bonded to thicken the structure, the tail component test was finished successfully.

5.5 Full-

The full-scale proof test was conducted. The fuselage structure used for the test is used for the flight program so the test load was limited up to 80% limit load. Six load cases (pressurization,

positive gust, positive gust with pressurization, rudder maneuver, rudder maneuver with pressurization, and two point landing) were selected, and six actuators of MTS Aero 90 system simulated design flight load as close as possible (Fig.18). Finally, the fuselage carried all load cases successfully. The strain, displacement, and reaction force data were measured and compared with those from the component tests and FEA. These data at the critical points showed good agreement, and extrapolated data were under the design allowables. Our flight safety assurance of the all-composite fuselage was completed when the full-scale proof test was finished.

6. CONCLUSION

The new concept all-composite fuselage structure was completed. Both the stiffened panel and the sandwich panel were arranged in the appropriate location and co-cured integrally. The estimated weight reduction was about 20% compared with a conventional aluminum structure. Also the affordable processes reduced the manufacturing cost.

The strength tests were conducted from the coupon level to the component level based on the Building Block Approach. Furthermore, the proof test of the fuselage for flight was conducted. As a result, safety of flight for the composite fuselage was proven.

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